

OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS – CAUSES AND EFFECTS ON PERINATAL OUTCOME**Prisacari Cristina***Student,**State University of Medicine and Pharmacy “Nicolae Testemițanu”***Abstract**

Oligohydramnios is a clinical condition manifested by a decrease in the level of amniotic fluid below the norm corresponding to the gestational age or an AFI less than 5 cm. The causes of this disorder include maternal, fetal and placental complications, all of them can lead to poor fetal outcomes. The decrease of the normal amniotic fluid volume, corresponding to the term of gestation, indicates the presence of maternal, fetal or placental conditions. One of the most common fetal causes of oligohydramnios are anomalies of the reno-urinary system, which constitute approximately 20% of all congenital fetal anomalies and occur in 3-4 % of pregnancies. Unilateral or bilateral renal agenesis, renal dysplasia and hypoplasia obstructiv uropathy, polycystic kidney disease – can be related to development of oligohydramnios. Intrauterine fetal growth restriction (IUGR) is another condition associated with an AFI less than 5 cm. IUGR represents a major obstetric problem, being associated with conditions such as prematurity, fetal distress, impairment of neuropsychic development or perinatal death.

Keywords: oligohydramnios, amniotic fluid index (AFI), maximal vertical pocket (MVM), intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM).

Introduction

The total volume of amniotic fluid results from the balance between its production and resorption. Until the 20 week of gestation, the largest amount of amniotic fluid is constituted by fetal lung secretions and maternal plasma. Around the 16 week of gestation fetal kidneys begin to function, so fetal urine makes up most of the amniotic fluid. Thus, various anomalies of the genitourinary system of the fetus, such as obstructive uropathy, renal dysplasia or renal agenesis can cause a low amniotic fluid level[8]. Oligohydramnios is associated with numerous complications in pregnancy, being often an indicator of various fetal, maternal or placental pathologies.

Quantification of amniotic fluid is an important component of the biophysical profile in USG evaluation of perinatal outcome. Transabdominal ultrasound evaluation of amniotic fluid volume includes maximal vertical pocket (MVM) or the amniotic fluid index (AFI), depending on the gestational age. The AFI can be determined after 20 weeks of gestation and its normal range is 5 to 25 cm, while normal range for MVM is 2 to 8 cm[2],[7]. Oligohydramnios often increases the risk of fetus distress and accompanies a wide range of reproductive disorders including anomalies of fetus and disorders of mother and placenta.

Aim of study

The aim of study was to analyse the fetal, maternal and placental causes of oligohydramnios and the fetal outcome in pregnant women with low amniotic fluid level at term.

Material and methods

A search in PubMed, Medline, EMBASE, and reference lists was performed. Inclusion criteria for articles selection: singleton pregnancy, definition of oligohydramnios as AFI less than 5cm, AF assessment at 37-42 gestational weeks.

Results

Oligohydramnios is associated with numerous maternal, fetal and placental complications of pregnancy. Maternal causes include chronic hypertension,

preeclampsia, vascular diseases, diabetes or the use of certain drugs such as NSAIDs, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, cytostatics and others[6]. Fetal causes of oligohydramnios include preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM) that accounts more than 37% of all pregnancies diagnosed with oligohydramnios. An important fetal complication associated with low amniotic fluid volume are genitourinary tract abnormalities. It includes renal agenesis, renal hypoplasia, obstructive nephropathy. The incidence of such complications is between 5 to 8 per 1000 live births. Intrauterine fetal growth restriction (IUGR) is another condition associated with an AFI less than 5 cm[3]. IUGR represents a major obstetric problem, being associated with conditions such as prematurity, fetal distress, impairment of neuropsychic development or perinatal death. Intrauterine fetal growth restriction leads to severe complications both in short and long term, being associated with serious metabolic, hematological, neurological disorders[1]. Placental causes of oligohydramnios include placental abruption and donor-transfused syndrome in monochorionic twin pregnancies. There are several additional complications to be aware of during the gestation complicated by oligohydramnios. These include an increased risk of cesarean delivery, fetal heart rate decelerations, or umbilical cord compression[4].

Conclusions

In conclusion, oligohydramnios is a serious clinical condition that increases the risk of perinatal complications. It frequently creates premises for the development of intrauterine growth restriction in addition to many pathological conditions, including congenital anomalies of kidney and urinary tract, low birth weight, CMV infection. Therefore, newborns with oligohydramnios demands intensive fetal surveillance and proper antepartum and intrapartum care.

Prognosis and therapeutic behavior depends on the etiology, the gestational age at the time of diagnosis and the degree of oligohydramnios. Diagnosing the condition in the third trimester is most often of idiopathic

origin. Thus, it can be stated that the topicality of the given theme and the necessity of researching the pathology in depth are determined not so much by the prevalence of oligohydramnios, but by the negative consequences it has on the intrauterine development of the fetus, maternal complications and the evolution of the pregnancy.

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